

Home Economics Education and Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners in the Kaputian District of Igacos

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the significant relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners. It employed the descriptive quantitative correlational method. The researcher used a random sampling method to conduct the study, selecting a proportional number of respondents from every public national high school in the Kaputian district, Division of Igacos Island Garden City of Samal, and everyone was chosen entirely by drawing lots. Due to the large population of learners in public schools in the Kaputian district, Division of Island Garden City of Samal, anyone can be chosen during the sampling process. The findings revealed that the extent of home economics education in terms of knowledge and awareness, cooking skills and practices, and health outcomes was extensive. The extent to which hands-on cooking skills among learners enhanced nutritional knowledge, changed dietary behaviors and fostered positive attitudes toward cooking and healthy eating was extensive. There was a significant relationship between home economics education and Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners. Research indicates that students enrolled in home economics programs demonstrate high cooking skills, improved problem-solving abilities, and enhanced sewing skills for economic empowerment. They may then continue to participate in school activities promoting their cooking skills.

KEY WORDS

1. Home Economics Education 2. Hands-On Cooking Skills

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1. Introduction

Home Economics Education, mainly through hands-on cooking skills, is pivotal in fostering healthy eating habits among learners. This education integrates practical skills, theoretical knowledge, and behavioral insights to promote a holistic understanding of nutrition, food preparation, and overall well-being. The importance of home economics education lies in its ability to empower individuals with the necessary tools to make informed decisions about their dietary choices and lifestyles. By engaging in hands-on cooking experiences learners gain a deeper appreciation for the entire food process, from selecting fresh ingredients to cooking and eventually enjoying the meals they prepare to reach the competency. In the global context, the impact of Home Economics Education on Healthy Eating Habits. A study published in the Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior found that hands-on cooking experiences in Home Economics Education significantly influenced individuals to adopt healthier eating habits. It highlights the correlation between practical cooking skills and

better dietary choices (Laska et al., 2019). The role of home economics curriculum in promoting healthy lifestyles. Research conducted by Raudenbush and Franko emphasizes the significance of integrating Home Economics Education into school curricula. They found that incorporating cooking experiences into the curriculum positively impacted students' attitudes toward healthy eating and cooking. "Influence of Home Economics Education on Teachers' and Students' Eating Habits. A longitudinal study by Perez-Rodrigo et al. assessed the dietary behaviors of teachers and students after participating in a Home Economics Education program. The study found that teachers not only improved their dietary behaviors, but their students also showed a significant shift toward healthier eating patterns. (Bleich, 2020). Home Economics Education, especially with hands-on cooking experiences, is a valuable tool in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners, influencing dietary behaviors, and promoting a better understanding of nutrition, cooking skills, and healthy eating in educational settings. A meta-analysis conducted by Wolfson and Bleich examined multiple studies on the relationship between cooking skills and healthy eating. Their findings support the notion that Home Economics Education and hands-on cooking significantly improve dietary behaviors among teachers and students (Raudenbush et al., 2019). In the national context, these studies collectively suggest that Home Economics Education, especially when combined with hands-on cooking experiences, is a valuable tool in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners, influencing dietary behaviors, and promoting a better understanding of nutrition and cooking skills (Koneru et al., 2021). Department of Education (DepEd) Philippines: Check the official DepEd website or their publications for any reports or studies related to the Home Economics curriculum and its impact on nutrition education. Local universities or research institutions should look into research conducted by universities or research institutions in the Philippines, particularly those focusing on education, nutrition, or public health (Gazaal et al., 2019). Academic Journals or Publications: Search for academic journals that specialize in education, home economics, or nutrition. Research articles from Filipino scholars or institutions might provide insights into this topic. By exploring these sources, you might find studies or reports that provide insights into Home Economics Education and hands-on cooking in promoting healthy eating habits among teachers and learners in the Philippines (Utter et al., 2020). In the educational context, it is important to distinguish between the notions of interdisciplinarity and multidisciplinary. The former is naturally integrative, while the latter is additive and juxtaposed, introducing multiple perspectives without supporting the integration of disciplinary knowledge throughout the curriculum (Klein, 2019). Lattuca, 2001; Spelt et al., (2019). Furthermore, transdisciplinary has an even wider perspective, as it is concerned with what lies between disciplines, across disciplines, and beyond all disciplines, intending to develop an overarching synthesis. The integrative nature of interdisciplinarity is actualized through various classroom implementation forms. As Mansilla (2019) observes, 'Interdisciplinary learners integrate information, data, techniques, tools, perspectives, concepts, and theories from two or more disciplines to craft products, explain phenomena, or solve problems in a way that would have been unlikely through single-disciplinary means.' This integration can only be supported in compulsory schools through interaction between subjects and pedagogical arrangements (Blackshields et al., 2019). The idea of integration, aimed at integrative thinking, is also closely connected to the idea of developing generic and, therefore, transferable skills. This is especially related to

higher education, which is gradually spreading elsewhere. For example, learning transversal competence is one of the cornerstones of the most recent Finnish National Core Curriculum for Basic Education (FNCC, 2019). However, the idea of context-free generic skills has been criticized, and research has suggested the need for domain-specific knowledge as the foundation for generic skills. To overcome this issue, Tynjala and Gijbels (2019) developed and proposed a model of integrative pedagogy applied to higher education, consisting of four key components of expertise: theoretical, practical, self-regulative, and sociocultural knowledge. These are meant to be integrated by creating learning environments in which mediating tools and pedagogical arrangements, such as learning tasks, help connect these knowledge types. The aim of combining these four types of knowledge can also be found in the curriculum of Finnish comprehensive schools (FNCC, 2019). Considering this study, the path towards a holistic and integrative approach to learning appears to be non-linear but somewhat different in the case of every school, teacher, and pupil. In addition to the pedagogical arrangements analyzed here, other elements affect the implementation of integrated learning in the classroom, such as differences in school cultures, teachers, pupil groups, and many others. Regardless of the starting point, sharing and analyzing ideas and experiences from diverse implementations offers opportunities to learn from each other, thereby enhancing development towards a more holistic, integrative approach to learning (Vitikka, E. 2019). This suggests that the teacher should choose the learning tasks carefully to ensure the best possible development. The observed lessons varied greatly in terms of their learning tasks and learning objectives. Interestingly, in the two most holistic lessons, the objectives already require an understanding of the integration among different subjects (Hall, 2019). Thus, it seems essential to plan learning tasks to support the integrative approach to learning, with the setting of suitable objectives forming a good starting point. Despite this, no explicit teacher-led integration was observed during the lesson. It is interesting to note that self-made pans have the potential to be used as supportive material tools for integration, as they could be used to combine the knowledge and skills of crafts and home economics. For example, during a discussion about the materials of the pans and the extent to which the different pans were suitable for frying (Taarnivaara, 2019). However, compared to the other observed lessons, this lesson had one distinctive element: the teaching and learning processes were conducted outside the classroom. This change altered the nature of the lesson, resulting in integration not being the primary objective of the lesson. Thus, its parallel structure was adequate to meet its objectives. Nonetheless, an example of student-led integration with mathematics occurred in this lesson when the students discussed how much milk they had added to the dough. During this discussion with their peers, the measuring cup allowed the students to learn the skill of measuring with different measuring cups in a home economics context (Vitikka, 2019). Additionally, mathematical knowledge was applied to solve a home economics problem. This example shows how home economics tasks naturally introduce knowledge from several subjects, even in a lesson that does not explicitly aim to integrate knowledge (Segovia, 2020). The purpose of this study is to assess the impact of home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. It will evaluate the influence of Home Economics Education and practical cooking experiences on the eating habits and nutritional awareness of both teachers and students. This involves measuring the effectiveness of these educational components in promoting healthier dietary behaviors (Taarnivaara, 2019).

To understand behavioral changes, investigate the changes in dietary patterns, food choices, meal planning, and nutritional knowledge resulting from participation in Home Economics programs among educators and students. This includes observing and analyzing shifts in attitudes towards healthy eating. Examine Educational Strategies: Explore the effectiveness of specific teaching methodologies, curricular approaches, or hands-on cooking activities in home economics classes. Assess how these strategies contribute to improving dietary habits within an educational setting (Tijbels, 2022). Contribute to Educational Policy and Practice: Inform educational policies or practices by providing empirical evidence and insights into the role of Home Economics Education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. The overarching goal of such a study is to contribute to understanding how Home Economics Education and practical cooking experiences influence dietary behaviors (Deeb et al., 2021).

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

This section summarizes significant literature related to Home Economics Education and its influence on healthy eating habits through interdisciplinary teaching methods. Key findings highlight how integrating subjects, such as Home Economics and language studies, enhances cultural understanding and cognitive development (Amaro et al., 2021; Venalainen, 2019). Tools like the samovar and pasha mold serve as both material and psychological tools, fostering integrative learning (Nikitina, 2019). Integration within teaching is emphasized, with concepts like interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity playing a pivotal role in synthesizing knowledge (Klein et al., 2022; Mansilla, 2019).

Studies have shown the need for pedagogical strategies that support the interaction of different disciplines, fostering interdisciplinary learners who integrate diverse perspectives (Saarnivaara, 2019; Gijbels, 2019). Vy-

gotsky's sociocultural learning theory further supports the importance of collaborative learning, emphasizing mediation through psychological tools like language to construct knowledge (Vygotsky, 1978).

In terms of nutritional knowledge, several studies identified the gap between awareness and behavior, especially among children and adolescents. Nutritional intake plays a crucial role in physical and cognitive development, with long-term effects on health outcomes. However, many students do not meet dietary recommendations, particularly in rural areas (Reicks et al., 2019; Wrieden et al., 2020). Differences in nutritional awareness between genders and age groups have been highlighted, with female students generally showing higher awareness but lower practical application (Carter et al., 2020).

Cooking skills have been linked to better diet quality and health outcomes. Learning these skills early in life is crucial for improving dietary behaviors and preventing chronic diseases. Research indicates that frequent home meal preparation leads to higher diet quality, with interventions focused on teaching cooking skills showing promise in enhancing health outcomes (Vitikka, 2021; Lavelle et al., 2020). Cooking confidence, particularly among adolescents involved in meal preparation, is associated with healthier food choices and better dietary outcomes (Tijhuis, 2022).

1.2. Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework—

This study is anchored in Albert Bandura's (1978) theory, which emphasizes the role of observational learning, self-efficacy, and behavioral modeling in shaping human behavior. In the context of Home Economics Education, it suggests that observing teachers and peers engaging in cooking activities can influence learners' perceptions and self-efficacy in preparing and choosing healthier meals. Second, the theory anchored in the study by David Kolb (2021) suggests that individuals learn by actively en-

gaging in experiences. Practical cooking experiences provided in Home Economics Education can offer a hands-on, experiential learning environment that fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation of healthy food choices, meal planning, and food preparation. In the context of Home Economics Education, it could guide the understanding of the process teachers and learners undergo when transitioning to healthier eating habits through stages such as pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance. The third theory is the model theory of Prochaska and DiClemente (1978), which focuses on the relationship between individuals' beliefs and their health-related behaviors. In the context of Home Economics Education, it suggests that by increasing learners' perceived susceptibility to health issues related to diet and promoting the perceived benefits of healthier eating, it can motivate changes in dietary behaviors. Developed by Prochaska and DiClemente, it outlines the stages individuals go through when changing behaviors. Lastly, the theory is the theory of Urie Bronfenbrenner. This theory considers the multiple layers of influence on an individual, including the microsystem (individual interactions), mesosystem (interactions between different microsystems), ecosystem (external environments), and macro system (cultural values and norms). Applied to Home Economics Education, this theory could examine how family, school, community, and societal influences impact dietary behaviors and the effectiveness of educational interventions. Figure 1 shows the relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. The first step in the quantitative analysis is to formulate a research question that will guide the study. For instance, the research question could be "Is there a significant relationship between

reading difficulties and the cognitive development of learners. The next step is to select a sample of learners who will participate in the study. The sample should be representative of the population of interest and large enough to ensure statistical significance. Data collection methods can include standardized tests to assess home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. The collected data can be analyzed using statistical methods such as correlation analysis, regression analysis, and descriptive statistics. The analysis will help establish the degree of correlation between home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. The results of the analysis can be used to draw conclusions and make recommendations on the best approaches to support learners with home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and students. For instance, the results may suggest that learners with reading difficulties may require additional support and interventions to enhance their cognitive development. In the theory of examining the relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners, it can provide valuable insights into the factors that affect learners' ability to acquire and process information. It can help educators understand the needs of learners with home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among students and teachers. These research indicators can be measured using various quantitative analysis methods, such as standardized tests, assessments, and surveys. By examining the relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners.

Fig. 1. The theoretical/ Conceptual Framework of the Study

1.3. *Statement of the Problem*—This study aims to determine the relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of home economics education in terms of?
 - (1) Nutritional knowledge and awareness,
 - (2) Cooking skills and practices, and
 - (3) Health outcomes?"
- (2) What is the extent of hands-on cooking skills among learners in terms of
 - (1) Enhanced Nutritional Knowledge;
 - (2) Changed dietary behaviors, and
 - (3) Positive Attitudes Towards Cooking and healthy eating?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners?

This study tested the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. H01: There is no significant relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners. The following terms are defined operationally to make this study more rational and practical: Home economics. This refers to an area that focuses on managing a household and family life. This includes learning skills such as cooking, cleaning, sewing, budgeting, child-rearing, and other practical tasks necessary for maintaining a home. Home economics aims to help individuals develop the knowledge and abilities to create a comfortable living environment while managing their finances effectively. This study teaches students how to prepare healthy meals for themselves and their fam-

ilies while keeping costs low. They can also develop skills in time management so they can balance work or school with household responsibilities. Home economics courses may cover nutrition, clothing care, interior design, personal finance, and more. Nutritional knowledge refers to pedagogical arrangements for promoting healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. It involves analyzing the impact of different teaching methods, such as project-based or inquiry-based learning, on students' attitudes toward healthy eating. Additionally, this study explores the role of interdisciplinary approaches in Home Economics Education and their potential to promote a holistic understanding of nutrition and cooking skills. Cooking skills and practices. This study identifies any challenges

or barriers that may hinder the implementation of Home Economics Education and hands-on cooking experiences in promoting healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. This includes examining funding, resources, teacher training, and cultural attitudes towards food. Behavioral changes in dietary habits in this study refer to the effectiveness of Home Economics Education and hands-on cooking experiences in promoting healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. This study can inform educational policies and practices to improve nutrition education by identifying successful strategies and potential barriers. This study assesses the participants' understanding of nutrition, meal planning, and the nutritional value of different foods. Assessment of participants' confidence in their ability to cook, plan meals, and make healthy food choices: Home Economics Education and its impact on participants' knowledge, skills, behaviors, and health outcomes. Improved Cooking Skills refer to assessing the effectiveness of home economics education and hands-on cooking experiences in promoting healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. This is a crucial area of research. This study aims to evaluate the impact of these educational components

on dietary behaviors, nutritional awareness, and attitudes toward healthy eating. Enhanced Nutritional Knowledge. This study assesses the improvement in understanding of nutrition, ingredient selection, and healthier meal choices after participants participate in hands-on cooking sessions. The changed dietary behaviors in this study refer to the evaluation of changes in dietary habits, including increased consumption of fruits and vegetables and healthier food choices due to participation in hands-on cooking activities. Positive attitudes toward cooking and healthy eating. This study refers to the assessment of improved attitudes and perceptions towards cooking and healthy eating. In addition to evaluating the impact of practical cooking experiences on healthy eating habits, this study will also examine specific teaching methodologies and curricular approaches. By exploring different educational strategies, we can identify which methods most effectively promote healthy eating behaviors among teachers and learners. Ultimately, this study aims to provide insights into how home economics education can be a valuable tool to foster healthy eating habits among teachers and learners.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The research design of this study utilized a quantitative, descriptive-correlational method because this study determines the relationship between home

economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners through quantitative analysis. To illustrate this research design, Creswell (2017) stated that it is a design used by investi-

gators to describe and measure the relationship between two variables or a set of scores. By using the universal sampling process, the study can be conducted differently. The researchers believe that a descriptive-correlational method is effective for this study. Through quantitative analysis, the researcher may be able to determine the relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking in fostering healthy eating habits among teachers and learners. It is the most appropriate design that can be used by the topic.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study's respondents were 250 secondary school learners within the Kaputian district, Division of Igacos, in the Island Garden City of Samal. The researcher set criteria for the inclusion of respondents. The respondents must be public secondary learners from five Kaputian District, Division of Igacos schools. Lastly, the respondents agreed to answer the survey tool administered by the researcher. The research respondents honestly filled out the information needed in the structured survey questionnaire that was distributed accordingly by the researcher. The researcher used a random sampling method to conduct the study, selecting a proportional number of respondents from every public national high school in the Kaputian district, Division of Igacos Island Garden City of Samal, and everyone was chosen entirely by drawing lots. Due to the large population of learners in public schools in the Kaputian district, Division of Island Garden City of Samal, anyone can be chosen during the

The second part of the instrument measures the extent of hands-on cooking skills among

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The necessary data underwent the following gathering procedure: The researcher asked the dean of the graduate school for endorsement to conduct the

sampling process.

2.3. Research Instrument—A researcher's self-made instrument was prepared with the guidance of the thesis adviser and evaluators and was used to gather the necessary data to realize the work. The questionnaire has three indicators for the independent variable (home economics education): nutritional knowledge and awareness, cooking skills and practices, and Health outcomes, while the dependent variable (hands-on cooking skills) considers the three indicators, namely enhanced nutritional knowledge, changed dietary behaviors, and positive attitudes towards cooking and healthy eating. Each indicator has five (5) questions that can be answered through the given legend. The questionnaires have simple instructions. The research questionnaires were purely researcher-made. A grammarian and validators submitted and evaluated the questionnaire concept. Suggestions and evaluation tools were provided to help the researchers improve and perfect the research instrument. The evaluation and validation outcomes, as well as the draft, were submitted to the research adviser for finalization. Unclear statements were removed, and weak statements were strengthened and polished. After the research adviser finalized it, the research instrument is now prepared. After the questionnaires are evaluated and approved, the researcher will administer the tool for gathering data and information from the respondents. The pilot testing was conducted in the same area but not with the study's respondents.

learners.

study. A letter request attached with the Dean's endorsement was forwarded to the School's Division Superintendent for permission. The researcher asked permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Divi-

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Home economics education is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Home economics education is often evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Home economics education is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Home economics education is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Home economics education is not provided.

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Hands-on cooking skills errors are always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Hands-on cooking skills are often evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Hands-on cooking skills are sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Hands-on cooking skills are rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Hands-on cooking skills are never evident.

sion of Island Garden City of Samal to survey the learners’ respondents. Likewise, the letter of permission granted by the Schools Division Superintendent was presented to the principals and supervisors of public schools in Kaputian district, Division of Island Garden City of Samal, for the arrangement of the research study’s conduct. The school principals and supervisors agreed to the arrangement upon observation of safety protocol regarding the conduct of the research. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the research survey tool. The researcher conducted the survey and retrieved the data. The researcher observed full ethical standards in the study, following the study protocol assessment and standardized criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The principals secured a copy of the letter presented to vouch that the researcher honestly con-

ducted and collected the data from the study respondents. The data gathered was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially accordingly. The results of this study were analyzed and interpreted based on its purpose. The responses were retrieved, tallied, and then forwarded to the statistician for data treatment. The teachers’ respondents from the Kaputian district, Division of Island Garden City of Samal, gave their free will to participate or withdraw from the study without any form of consequence or penalties. The respondents personally and professionally gave information that may be required in the study, which was kept private and treated with the utmost confidentiality of the respondents’ data, which was adhered to. On the other hand, the research questionnaire used is free of technical terms and can be easily understood by the study’s respondents, prevent-

ing perceived biases. Therefore, no research questionnaire was given to respondents without permission from the authorized command channels.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools may be used to treat the data: This may be to determine the extent of home economics education and hands-on cooking skills

among learners. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation. This tool may be used to determine the relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners. Regression. This tool may be used to determine the role of home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the findings of this study. They were thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted.

3.1. *The extent of home economics education in terms of Nutritional knowledge and awareness*—Table 1 shows the data on the extent of home economics education in terms of Nutritional knowledge and awareness. The presentation of the result focuses on the indicators with the highest and lowest mean ratings as follows: Home Economics Education supports the development of practical skills to plan and prepare nutritious meals, fostering greater nutritional awareness and healthier eating habits among participants as the highest mean rating of 4.11 or extensive. Participants engaged in Home Economics Education demonstrated an increased understanding of dietary guidelines, leading to more informed food choices and

healthier meal planning as the lowest mean rating but still had an extensive mean rating of 3.76. This has gained an overall mean rating of 3.96 or extensive, meaning that the extent of home economics education in terms of Nutritional knowledge and awareness is often observed. Further, the finding reveals that respondents on this indicator emphasize the importance of aligning their actions, purpose, and direction with the students to support physical development. In home economics education, students learn which nutrients are necessary for human health and maintenance of life and which food includes such nutrients, as well as the knowledge, skills, and techniques related to cooking that make it possible to enjoy eating foods without reducing the nutrient value.

This finding is similar to the published Worsley, Wang, Yeatman, Byrne, and Wijayaratne (2016) findings from both studies, which strongly suggest that health or home economics education is related to the various forms of food knowledge. The replication of the findings from Study 1 by the shorter scores from Study 2 suggests that these relationships are relatively stable between samples, and the size of the relationships appears similar to those associated with general education and the presence of children in the household. The inter-

pretation of these findings, however, requires caution. At face value, the results suggest that home economics (or similar) education may result in people having food knowledge than those who have not undergone such education. Given the content of home economics education, this is an entirely reasonable explanation. However, other explanations for these correlations may be equally plausible. For example, respondents who were more interested in food and health matters may have selected to undertake these forms of education or may have been more at-

Table 1. Extent of Home Economics Education in Terms of Nutritional Knowledge and Awareness

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Home Economics Education significantly improves participants' understanding of balanced nutrition, food labels, and the nutritional value of various food groups.	4.01	Extensive
2	Home Economics classes provide essential knowledge about portion control, the significance of crucial nutrients, and their role in maintaining overall health.	4.00	Extensive
3	Participants engaged in Home Economics Education demonstrate an increased awareness of dietary guidelines, leading to more informed food choices and healthier meal planning.	3.76	Extensive
4	The curriculum in Home Economics equips learners with the ability to evaluate food information critically, understand the impact of different diets on health, and make informed decisions regarding their nutritional intake.	3.93	Extensive
5	Home Economics Education supports the development of practical skills to plan and prepare nutritious meals, fostering greater nutritional awareness and healthier eating habits among participants.	4.11	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.96	Extensive

tentive to the information provided in the various courses they undertook. However, a report from the UK Cabinet Office in 2008 marks a renewal of emphasis on food issues (UK Cabinet Office, 2008). The report noted that food is integral to environmental and agricultural policy, health and safety, and social and foreign policy. A key point made in the report is that an integrated approach to food is required, including an understanding of the multifaceted roles of food in daily life and national and international affairs. Thorough and comprehensive knowledge of food is usually provided in home economics curricula to enable future citizens to choose safe and healthy foods that do not harm their families, other humans or animals, and the

environment (Smith De Zwart, 2010).

3.2. *Cooking skills and practices*—Table 2 presents data on the extent of home economics education regarding cooking skills and practices. The presentation of the result focuses on the indicators with the highest and lowest mean ratings as follows: Home Economics Education enhances students' understanding of nutritional labels and their application in making healthier food choices as the highest mean rating of 4.09 or extensive. On the other hand, through Home Economics, learners develop proficiency in meal planning, portion control, and selecting healthy ingredients, contributing to a more balanced diet. They got the lowest mean rating of 3.98 but still have extensive descriptions.

Table 2. Extent of Home Economics Education Regarding Cooking Skills and Practices

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Home Economics Education enhances students' understanding of nutritional labels and their application in making healthier food choices.	4.09	Extensive
2	Home Economics education instills fundamental cooking skills, enabling individuals to understand cooking techniques and meal preparation from scratch.	3.99	Extensive
3	Home Economics equips participants with the ability to follow recipes, adapt them to their personal dietary needs, and experiment with ingredients to create balanced and nutritious meals.	4.00	Extensive
4	Through Home Economics, learners develop proficiency in meal planning, portion control, and the selection of healthy ingredients, contributing to a more balanced diet.	3.98	Extensive
5	Students engaged in Home Economics classes learn essential culinary skills, including knife handling, food safety, and various cooking methods such as baking, sautéing, and grilling.	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.01	Extensive

Collectively, the overall mean is 4.01 with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive, which means that the extent of home economics education in terms of cooking skills and practices is oftentimes manifested. The results suggest that the cooking skills considered important in-home economics in the Philippines include sensory evaluation, traditional cooking techniques, and adherence to food safety practices. This finding is similar to the study of Cunningham-Sabo and Simons (2012) on the importance of learning cooking skills at an early age for skill retention, confidence, cooking practices, cooking attitude, and diet quality. Mothers remained the primary source of learning; however, as there has been a reported deskilling of domestic cooks, mothers may no longer be able to teach cooking skills to the next generation. A focus on alternative sources, including practical cooking skills education starting at an early age, is required. This

study also highlights the need for further longitudinal research on the impact of age and source of learning on cooking skills. Cooking skills are increasingly included in strategies to prevent and reduce chronic diet-related diseases and obesity. While cooking interventions target all age groups (Child, Teen, and Adult), the optimal age for learning these skills on 1) skills retention, 2) cooking practices, 3) cooking attitudes, 4) diet quality, and 5) health is unknown. Similarly, although the source of learning cooking skills has been previously studied, the differences in learning from these sources have not been considered. This research investigated the associations between age and source of learning with the five factors above.

3.3. *Health Outcomes*—Table 3 shows data on the extent of home economics education regarding health outcomes. The presentation of the result focuses on the indicators with the high-

est and lowest mean ratings as follows. Home Economics cultivates confidence in individuals to cook and explore diverse cuisines, fostering a lifelong appreciation for homemade, healthy meals with the highest mean rating of 4.08. Home Economics education empowers learners to comprehend the relationship between cooking techniques, ingredient quality, and the overall nutritional value of prepared meals as the lowest mean rating of 3.96 but has extensive

mean rating. This has gained an overall mean of 4.01 or more, with the descriptive equivalent of oftentimes observed, which means that the teacher fully understands Home economics education plays a crucial role in shaping healthy eating habits among adolescents. Research indicates that home economics teachers recognize the significance of food literacy, encompassing knowledge and skills, in influencing food choices and health outcomes.

Table 3. Extent of Home Economics Education in Terms of Health Outcomes

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Home Economics cultivates confidence in individuals to cook and explore diverse cuisines, fostering a lifelong appreciation for homemade, healthy meals.	4.08	Extensive
2	Home Economics classes gain practical experience in meal budgeting, time management, and resourceful cooking practices, promoting efficient and economical meal preparation.	4.03	Extensive
3	Home Economics emphasizes the importance of practical cooking knowledge, allowing individuals to troubleshoot cooking issues, understand food interactions, and improvise in the kitchen.	3.99	Extensive
4	Students exposed to Home Economics cooking activities are encouraged to embrace a hands-on approach to cooking, leading to a greater understanding of food chemistry and its role in successful meal preparation.	4.01	Extensive
5	Home Economics education empowers learners to comprehend the relationship between cooking techniques, ingredient quality, and the overall nutritional value of prepared meals.	3.96	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.01	Extensive

This is supported by the study of Yoko SUZUKI (2014) the world. However, while some people suffer from hunger, other people suffer from lifestyle-related illnesses due to overnutrition. Among the advanced nations, which are in the latter situation, food and nutrition education to improve people’s dietary habits has been promoted in various countries, as evidenced by the Slow Food movement in

Italy, which began in the late 1980s, and classes on taste called “Leçon de Goût” in France, which started in 1990. Also, the Basic Law on Shokuiku was enacted in Japan in 2005. The Law defines “Shokuiku” as education to acquire knowledge of food and nutrition, as well as the ability to choose appropriate foods through various food-related experiences, in order to improve people’s ability to practice healthy eating

habits (from “What is “Shokuiku (Food Education)”?). The targets of the Law are not only children but citizens of all ages. This report describes “Shokuiku” as “food and nutrition education.” Unfavorable dietary habits, as evidenced by the number of people suffering from metabolic syndrome, have not decreased, which is one of the reasons for the rising healthcare expenditure in Japan. Facing a growing discrepancy between food production, such as agriculture and fisheries, and food consumption, Japan has an extremely low food self-sufficiency rate, which poses a serious social problem. Filling a gap between production and consumption will decrease CO2 emissions from transportation and reduce the environmental burden. Furthermore, it will have a positive impact on safety. Many things should be passed down to the next generation, such as local food and food eaten at seasonal events.

3.4. *Summary of the Home Economics Education*—Table 4 presents data on the summary

of home economics education. The overall mean of 4.00 is extensive or often observed, distributed by the indicators. The indicators were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: DepEd knowledge and awareness (3.96), cooking skills and practices (4.01), and Safe and Health Outcomes (4.01); all of these indicators have the descriptive equivalent of Extensive. This finding reveals that home economics education instills a sense of responsibility and independence in students as they learn to manage their own households and make informed choices. Moreover, it can contribute to the overall well-being of students by teaching them about nutrition, health, and personal hygiene. Home economics education plays a crucial role in shaping healthy eating habits among adolescents. Research indicates that home economics teachers recognize the significance of food literacy, encompassing knowledge and skills, in influencing food choices and health outcomes.

Table 4. Summary of Home Economics Education

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Knowledge and Awareness	3.96	Extensive
Cooking Skills and Practices	4.01	Extensive
Health Outcomes	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.99	Extensive

This finding is supported by Worsley et al.’s (2016) findings that home economics and health teachers are found in many parts of the world. They teach students about food’s nutritional, safety, and environmental properties. The effects of such teaching might be expected to be reflected in the food knowledge of adults who have undertaken school education in these areas. This study examined the food knowledge associations of school home economics and health education among Australian adults. They added that the results of their study were that two

separate online surveys were conducted nationwide among 2022 (November 2011) and 2146 Australian adults (November–December 2012). Both surveys’ true/false and multiple-choice questions assessed nutrition, food safety, and environmental knowledge. Knowledge scores were constructed and compared against respondents’ experience of school health or home economics education via multiple regression analyses. Both studies showed that home economics (and similar) education was associated with higher levels of food knowledge among

several age groups.

3.5. *The Extent of Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners In Terms of Enhanced Nutritional Knowledge* —Table 5 presents the data on the extent of hands-on cooking skills—the learners in terms of enhanced nutritional knowledge. The presentation of the result focuses on the indicators with the highest and lowest mean ratings as follows: Through Home Economics classes, participants develop the ability to adapt cooking methods to vari-

ous dietary requirements, ensuring inclusivity and diversity in meal preparation skills as the highest mean rating with 4.03, and hands-on cooking provides a firsthand understanding of the nutritional value of ingredients, empowering individuals to make informed, healthier choices while preparing meals as the lowest mean rating of 3.98 but still describe as extensive. All items under this indicator obtain mean results with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive.

Table 5. Extent of Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners in Terms of Enhanced Nutritional Knowledge

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Through Home Economics classes, participants develop the ability to adapt cooking methods to various dietary requirements, ensuring inclusivity and diversity in meal preparation skills.	4.03	Extensive
2	Hands-on cooking provides a firsthand understanding of the nutritional value of ingredients, empowering individuals to make informed, healthier choices while preparing meals.	3.98	Extensive
3	Engaging in cooking enhances the comprehension of balanced nutrition, leading to better meal planning and the creation of well-rounded, nutritious dishes.	4.02	Extensive
4	Through practical cooking experiences, individuals develop.	4.01	Extensive
5	Home Economics nurtures cooking skills, promotes practical culinary knowledge, and fosters a deeper understanding of cooking practices among individuals.	4.00	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.01	Extensive

This has gained an overall mean of 4.01 with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive and the descriptive equivalent of often observed. This means that the teacher in this indicator agreed that cooking skills are associated with better diet quality and health status. It can also reduce anxiety and stress, especially during uncertain times. Additionally, cooking at home promotes family ties and strengthens relation-

ships. In summary, cooking skills may help people meet nutrition guidelines in their daily nutrition supply and allow them to make healthier food choices. Therefore, teaching children and teenagers how to cook and encouraging them to develop their cooking skills is essential. Cooking is a valuable life skill often linked with improved diet quality, such as improving the uptake of fruit and vegetables and increased recog-

nutrition of healthier foods (Lang T, Caraher 2001). In a UK survey of 2000 residents, ‘learn to cook’ was rated as the fifth most crucial life skill for modern living (the highest non-tech skill), following ‘searching the internet,’ ‘operating a mobile phone,’ ‘connecting WiFi’ and ‘mastering online banking,’ demonstrating public interest in learning cooking skills. Cooking skills (CS) have been increasingly used on their own and as part of other initiatives as a preventive measure to address diet-related diseases, including obesity. In recent years, there has been an increase in CS and food skills (FS) interventions to improve dietary outcomes. Current reviews on cooking intervention studies indicate that these interventions vary in teaching methods, such as information provision, demonstrations, and practical hands-on sessions. They have been targeted at people of all ages, including children (McGowan et al., 2013), teenagers, and adults. While the rationale for targeting these groups is clearly stated in each intervention, the optimal age for learning CS about cooking skill maintenance and dietary outcomes is unknown (Nelson et al., 2013).

3.6. Changed Dietary Behaviors—Table 6 presents data on how hands-on cooking skills are used regarding changed dietary behaviors. The presentation is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings obtained: The curriculum in Home Economics education equips individuals with a diverse range of cooking techniques, fostering a comprehensive understanding of food preparation, with the highest mean rating of 4.01 or extensive. At the same time, Home Economics emphasizes practical, hands-on experiences, cultivating skills in recipe execution, ingredient selection, and adapting recipes to personal dietary preferences, with the lowest mean rating of 3.78 or extensive. This has gained an overall mean of 3.89 with a descriptive equivalent of extensive, which means that by learning how to make healthier and more mindful choices, you may be able to manage

compulsive eating, bingeing, and weight gain. Moreover, it protects you against chronic non-communicable diseases like heart disease, diabetes, and cancer. Eating various foods and consuming less salt, sugars, and saturated and industrially-produced trans-fats are essential for a healthy diet. A healthy diet comprises a combination of different foods. Eating healthy can also give you more energy daily, may help you lose weight, and can affect your mental health. Diet is one of the most significant factors people can change to improve their quality of life, both daily and long-term. The finding affirms that Mozaffarian (2016) that promoting dietary behavior change first requires a sound evidence base for the relationship between dietary factors and disease. This evidence base exposes both beneficial and detrimental factors. When people consume food, multiple chemical compounds are delivered to the body and interact with various physiological and metabolic processes. Trujillo et al. (2006) affirmed that a substantial amount of research has been conducted on how foods and food components influence pathways and mechanisms of action related to cardiovascular and metabolic health. A recent review of dietary and policy priorities for cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and obesity noted that, to date, several nutritional factors are known to influence health.⁴ These included 11 foods that appeared to have a positive impact (fruit, vegetables, nuts, whole grains, legumes, fish, shellfish, yogurt, cheese, milk, vegetable oils) and a couple of others that may be detrimental (refined grains, processed meats). Food components and beverages that would be beneficial (such as phytochemicals and coffee) or detrimental (such as excess sodium and sugary beverages) were also identified. However, the impact of food preparation, food processing, and dietary patterns must be considered. The pathways and mechanisms by which these dietary factors exerted their influence included glucose-insulin homeostasis, blood lipids, blood pressure, and the functions

of the endothelial, cardiac, and adipocyte systems, the gut microbiome, systemic inflammation and hunger, and satiety.

Table 6. Extent of Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners in Terms of Changed Dietary Behaviors

No.	Statement	Mean (x)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Home Economics imparts foundational cooking skills essential for meal preparation and culinary understanding.	4.00	Extent
2	The curriculum in Home Economics education equips individuals with a diverse range of cooking techniques, fostering a comprehensive understanding of food preparation.	4.01	Extent
3	Students engaged in Home Economics learn cooking basics and advanced skills such as meal planning, food safety, and nutritionally balanced meal preparation.	3.79	Extent
4	Home Economics emphasizes practical, hands-on experiences, cultivating skills in recipe execution, ingredient selection, and adapting recipes to personal dietary preferences.	3.78	Extent
5	Through Home Economics, participants develop proficiency in various culinary methods such as baking, sautéing, roasting, and other cooking techniques.	3.88	Extent
Overall Mean		3.89	Extent

This finding is supported by Fisheries (2010), who explains that flexibility and differentiation to meet the needs of individual students are the core aspects of student-centered learning. Instructional strategies should combine new and innovative ideas and best practices based on the needs of the students. Differentiated instruction ensures that what a student learns, how he/she learns, and how the student demonstrates what he/she has learned matches that student’s readiness.

3.7. *Positive Attitudes Toward Cooking and Healthy Eating*—Presented in Table 9 are data on the extent of hands-on cooking skills among learners in terms of positive attitudes toward cooking and healthy eating. The state-

ments in the indicator are logically presented with a concentration on the highest and the lowest mean computation, as follows: The practical experience gained in Home Economics classes extends beyond cooking skills, encompassing resource management, budgeting, and time-efficient meal preparation, with the highest mean rating of 4.01 while Home Economics focuses on teaching cooking methods and fostering an understanding of the relationship between ingredients, cooking processes, and the final meal is the lowest mean rating of 3.67 describe as extensive. The overall mean of 3.86 is described as comprehensive, meaning the extent of positive attitudes toward cooking and healthy eating is often observed.

Table 7. Extent of Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners in Terms of Positive Attitudes Toward Cooking and Healthy Eating

No.	Statement	Mean (x)	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Home Economics education nurtures creativity in the kitchen, encouraging individuals to experiment with flavors and ingredients, leading to the development of personal cooking styles.	3.71	Extensive
2	The practical experience gained in Home Economics classes extends beyond cooking skills, encompassing resource management, budgeting, and time-efficient meal preparation.	4.01	Extensive
3	Home Economics focuses on teaching cooking methods and fostering an understanding of the relationship between ingredients, cooking processes, and the final meal.	3.67	Extensive
4	Students enrolled in Home Economics are encouraged to appreciate food’s cultural diversity, explore various cuisines, and expand their culinary knowledge.	3.89	Extensive
5	The skills acquired through Home Economics instill confidence in individuals to plan and prepare meals, promoting a lifelong appreciation for homemade, nutritious food and sustainable cooking practices.	3.99	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.86	Extensive

Healthy meals at home can support your immune system and reduce the risk of illnesses such as heart disease, cancer, high blood pressure, and diabetes. It can give you more energy, improve sleep at night, and help you better manage health problems. This finding is supported by Individuals’ cooking and food preparation skills, which were evaluated using the “Cooking Skills and Food Skills” scale. This scale was developed by Lavelle et al. (2017). Keleş Akçil (2021) examined the reliability and validity of the Turkish scale. The Cronbach’s alpha internal consistency coefficient of the scale is 0.954. The scale consists of 33 questions and has two sub-factors: cooking and food skills. The cooking skills sub-factor consists of 14 items, and the food skills sub-factor consists of 19 items. The scale is scored with an 8-point Likert system ranging from 1 (very bad) to 7 (very good) with

a never/rarely option. Participants are asked to rate how good they are at each skill, and scores between 1 and 7 are added for the skills used.

3.8. *Summary of the Extent of Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners*—Table 8 summarizes the extent of hands-on cooking skills among learners. The summary results are presented in the following manners: Enhanced Nutritional Knowledge, with a mean rating of 3.91, has a descriptive equivalent of high, while Changed Dietary Behaviors has a mean rating of 3.87. Moreover, Positive Attitudes Toward Cooking and Healthy Eating has a mean rating of 3.86. This finding reveals that teacher respondents agree and support why Hands-On Cooking Skills are considered the most significant factor in the students’ nutritional source of foods.

The result corroborates Clifford Astbury et

al.'s (2019) statement that healthy nutrition is essential at every stage of life to protect and develop health and increase the quality of life. It is stated that inadequate and unbalanced nutrition causes obesity and other non-communicable diseases related to nutrition (such as Type II diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and some types of cancer (Besler et al., 2015). A healthy and balanced diet requires many skills in planning meals and purchasing and preparing food.

Table 8. Summary of the Extent of Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners

Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Equivalent
Enhanced Nutritional Knowledge	3.91	Extensive
Changed Dietary Behaviors	3.87	Extensive
Positive Attitudes Toward Cooking and Healthy Eating	3.86	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.89	Extensive

The finding conforms with the statement of Heifetz and Linsky (2002), who say that these competencies enable classroom leaders to be conscious of personal limitations and use individual strengths to further the work of achieving organizational goals.

3.9. *Significant Relationship Between Home Economics Education and Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners* —Presented in Table 9 are data on the significant relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient used with the computed r-value for the home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners is 0.52. This denotes a moderate relationship, as its p-value of 0.032 is less than the 0.05 significance level. It is

statistically significant at a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$; the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is an essential relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners. The result implies that home economics education affects hands-on cooking skills among learners. Home economics education plays a significant role in enhancing students' cooking skills. Research conducted in Nigeria found that most home economics students possessed high cooking skills, indicating the effectiveness of education in developing culinary abilities. Research indicates that students enrolled in home economics programs demonstrate high cooking skills, improved problem-solving abilities, and enhanced sewing skills for economic empowerment.

This finding is supported by Ejeabukwa (2022), who stressed that home economics is an essential part of learning in the colleges of education in the Nigerian higher education landscape. It allows the learners to acquire basic home training required in contemporary societies. However, little is known about the cooking potential of students enrolled in home eco-

nomics. The present study assessed the cooking skills of home economics students in colleges of education in southeast Nigeria. Ninety-seven students were recruited from home economics departments in colleges of education in the southeast. The respondents completed a self-report measure of cooking skills. The percentage analysis showed that most students

Table 9. Significant Relationship Between Home Economics Education and Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners

Variables	Pearson r	Degree of Correlation	P-value @0.05	Decision
Home Economics Education Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners	0.52	High	0.032	Reject Ho

(61.11) This finding is supported by Alpaugh Pope et al. (2020), who stressed that home economics is an essential part of learning in the colleges of education in the Nigerian higher education landscape. It allows the learners to acquire basic home training required in contemporary societies. Students enrolled in home economics in college education are exposed to various cooking styles and dietary knowledge. Thus, the students are trained to acquire necessary skills relating to cooking, dietary behavior, health maintenance, and eating behavior. The

field of home economics has taken a new dimension to meet today’s human needs in its present development and potential values. It prepares learners to be self-reliant and self-employed. It equips the students with essential cooking skills. Thus, cooking skills taught in colleges of education in Nigeria are crucial as they affect self-reliability, nutritional knowledge, dietary behavior, quality, and personal health. It also involves the home meal preparation and consumption process and how a household can handle stressful situations.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter summarizes the study’s findings, conclusions, and recommendations. The study aimed to determine whether there is a significant relationship between home economics education and hands-on cooking skills among learners. It employed the descriptive quantitative correlational method.

4.1. *Findings*—The researcher used a random sampling method to conduct the study, selecting a proportional number of respondents from every public national high school in the Kaptian district, Division of Igacos Island Garden City of Samal, and everyone was chosen entirely by drawing lots. Due to the large population of learners in public schools in the Kaptian district, Division of Island Garden City of Samal, anyone can be chosen during the sampling process. The extent of Home Economics Education in terms of knowledge and awareness, 3.96; cooking skills and practices, 4.01; and Health Outcomes, 4.01, with an overall mean

of 3.99 or extensive The Extent of hands-on cooking skills among learners enhanced nutritional knowledge, 3.91, changed dietary behaviors and positive attitudes toward cooking, 3.87, and healthy eating, 3.86. with an overall mean of 3.86 or extensive. There was a significant relationship between home economics education and Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners, with a probability value of 0.032, meaning it is outside the acceptance region.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the overall findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The extent of home economics education in terms of knowledge and awareness,

cooking skills and practices, and health outcomes was extensive. The extent to which hands-on cooking skills among learners enhanced nutritional knowledge, changed dietary behaviors and fostered positive attitudes toward cooking and healthy eating was extensive. There was a significant relationship between home economics education and Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered for consideration: School heads' supervisory skills improve successfully with the support of Department of Education Officials by continuously conducting related institutionalized programs and activities aligned with home economics. School heads may maintain extensive home economics education regarding knowledge and awareness, cooking skills and practices, and health outcomes. Home

education teachers may continue to improve their practical skills in teaching the subjects, especially cooking skills. Beyond the practical skills, cooking builds character. It encourages students to work with others to produce the final result and boosts their confidence as they take the lead in packing their lunches, baking holiday treats, or helping to get dinner on the table. Home economics education plays a crucial role in developing students' skills. Research indicates that students enrolled in home economics programs demonstrate high cooking skills, improved problem-solving abilities, and enhanced sewing skills for economic empowerment. They may then continue to participate in school activities promoting their cooking skills. Lastly, a similar or comparative study exploring other indicators is suggested to develop home economics education and Hands-On Cooking Skills Among Learners.

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